

**REVIEW OF HEALTHCARE FINANCING SYSTEMS IN DEVELOPED COUNTRIES WITH THE
PURPOSE OF DEVELOPING CURRENT SYSTEM IN THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN**

Zabirova E.

DBA Doctoral Student

Almaty Management University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Nogayev N.

MBA

Almaty Management University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Abstract

Reducing wasteful spending has become a key topic in the healthcare financing debate. A special OECD report was devoted to this issue, demonstrating that wasteful spending can be found at all levels of the healthcare system. Specifically, it notes the need to combat largely preventable medical errors, the inappropriate use of antimicrobials, and unjustified changes in medical practice. For example, expanding the use of paramedics in certain areas could lead to cost savings without negatively impacting the quality of care. Main development directions are observed in this article which are possible to be implemented in Kazakhstani healthcare financial system in order to improve current healthcare system in general.

Keywords: Healthcare management, financial system of healthcare, healthcare in Kazakhstan, financing of healthcare, foreign experience.

Changes in market entry and prescribing regulations facilitate the increased use of generics, thereby saving on pharmaceutical costs. Health technology assessments (HTAs) will help avoid the introduction of cost-ineffective new technologies, and existing cost-ineffective measures will be eliminated. Digitalization can support new methods of delivering healthcare, particularly in the form of telemedicine (which has rapidly expanded in many countries due to the pandemic) and robotic tools for certain limited procedures. Furthermore, organizational changes in intensive care resource management and the increased use of simulations developed during the pandemic are leading to more efficient use of limited hospital resources.

It appears that the greatest interest lies in finding new sources of funding within existing systems, which is largely linked to increased private financing. Most notably, the development of supplementary private health insurance, whereby "the state encourages citizens to take their own actions and pay for medical services in order to ease pressure on the public system and increase overall national healthcare spending."

In developed countries, private health insurance programs vary, but are generally supplementary to public ones and voluntary. They currently account for approximately 10% of healthcare spending on average in OECD countries, although there is considerable variation across countries. Private health insurance accounts for a third of all healthcare spending in the United States, approximately 60% in the Netherlands, and almost half in Switzerland. In approximately half of OECD countries, it accounts for 5% of expenditures or less, while in the Czech Republic, Estonia, and Sweden, it is practically nonexistent [1].

Private health insurance in developed countries mostly plays a secondary role, providing coverage for services not included in public programs or where co-payments are required, or duplicating coverage of public services to provide faster access or increased choice of doctor or health care provider.

Incentives primarily include tax breaks for those who pay contributions. However, global experience

shows that, despite its apparent simplicity, this solution has a number of limitations. Using public funds to pay for tax breaks diverts resources from the public healthcare system, resulting in the need to either raise taxes or reduce spending elsewhere to compensate for the lost revenue. Therefore, the need to finance tax breaks will likely increase public spending. Administrative costs are higher with private health insurance, as a complex organizational system is required to assess risk, determine premiums, develop plans, etc.

Private health insurance shifts the burden of payment from the healthy, young, and wealthy to the poor, old, and sick, as costs increase with age. Therefore, in practice, insurance is too expensive for people over a certain age and with certain chronic conditions. It benefits those who can afford it, i.e., the wealthier citizens. Tax incentives in this case are inherently regressive, offering public subsidies to the wealthier and are meaningless for the poor. The data showed that healthcare financing systems built primarily on private health insurance, such as in the United States and Switzerland, were the most regressive compared to tax-based systems. Countries with tax-based financing had the least regressive healthcare financing systems [2].

Among the possible mechanisms for financing healthcare, it is worth noting the so-called co-payments when the patient, even if covered by insurance or tax programs, directly pays part of the costs, usually at the time of receiving the service.

Although one of the reasons for introducing co-payments was to increase revenue, it is not entirely clear whether they are intended to offset rising healthcare costs or represent an additional source of revenue to public funds for healthcare financing. However, the impact of co-payments on the use of health services is important, with the aim of preventing overuse. Therefore, they can also be considered as a means of rationing services. It should be noted that sufficiently high co-payments do reduce service utilization. However, according to the WHO, the introduction of co-payments leads to rationing of the use of specific ser-

vices but does not ensure rationalization of overall consumer demand. Concerns have arisen about their negative impact on the well-being of patients and healthcare institutions, as co-payments can impair access to health services. Lower utilization and delayed seeking medical care can ultimately increase demand for more expensive care and lead to increased costs in the long term. These effects can be mitigated by establishing exceptions to co-payments, particularly for low-income groups, but this can create inequality for those above the threshold and generally reduce their impact on both behavior and spending. It should be noted that collecting co-payments requires certain administrative costs. In 1992, New Zealand introduced hospital bed charges, but difficulties in collecting payments from patients led to their abolition less than a year later. In France, residents purchase supplementary insurance to cover various co-payments, negating the very idea of introducing them [3].

A mechanism is possible under which patients would be given the option to pay a portion of the total cost of treatment or individual medical services that exceed the thresholds for state-funded expenses. This solution takes into account the limited state resources while simultaneously making certain medical care options available to patients that would otherwise be unavailable.

Recently, researchers have increasingly focused on the behavioral consequences of introducing copayments, such as reduced prescription drug use and physician visits. Empirical evidence on whether the overall use of services subject to copayments is reduced or replaced by free services is highly inconclusive. However, the distributional consequences of copayments are noted: low-income individuals tend to reduce their use of services relatively more than the rest of the population when copayments are in place. Copayments influence medication initiation and continuation, and the higher the copayment, the lower the treatment adherence. Therefore, the broader impact of copayments as a cost-sharing mechanism on treatment adherence, clinical outcomes, resource utilization, and overall costs must be considered [4].

Taxes on the consumption of unhealthy products, or public health taxes, are excise taxes levied on goods that may harm public health. These include tobacco products, alcohol, sugar-added beverages such as soft drinks, tea, flavored coffee, juices, and sports drinks. The harmful effects of these products on health are well-studied and supported by research. These taxes are aimed at reducing their consumption, generating additional revenue for the healthcare system, and improving public health [3].

After introducing a tax on the consumption of unhealthy products or modeling their potential impact, almost all studies found a decrease in the consumption of potentially harmful products. Revenues increased in almost all countries, suggesting additional scope for tax increases. Calculations showed improvements in population health, revealing a correlation between increased taxes on unhealthy products and a reduction in the prevalence of diabetes, stroke, heart attacks, and related deaths [5].

While there are differences in the extent of implementation and outcomes between low- and middle-income and high-income countries, the data show that the introduction of such taxes can have a significant impact on consumption patterns and well-being, while ensuring fiscal sustainability. From an economic perspective, excise taxes are a form of indirect taxation, as they are levied on goods or services rather than on individuals or businesses. Taxes on the consumption of unhealthy products can be applied in two different ways: per unit (defined as a fixed amount for each unit of a good or service sold, for example, in dollars per kilogram) or *ad valorem* (levied on expenditures and set as a percentage of value added). In the former case, the tax is a fixed amount, while in the latter case, it is a fixed percentage per unit of the product [6].

These taxes represent one way to raise revenue; their use allows countries to channel financial resources into public spending without putting pressure on other expenditure items or disrupting fiscal balance. Two products stand out in this regard: alcohol and tobacco.

Increased government revenues were the driving force behind the introduction of taxes on alcohol and tobacco consumption. For example, high tobacco consumption and the relatively low elasticity of demand for tobacco products (i.e., the disproportionate response of tobacco consumption to a moderate price increase), along with the small number of producers, made these products particularly attractive targets for taxation. However, emerging evidence of the negative health consequences of tobacco and alcohol consumption has transformed tobacco and alcohol taxation into a tool for reducing their consumption. Tobacco taxation is highly cost-effective, combining the potential for a significant impact on tobacco consumption with low implementation costs. The WHO also recommends increasing taxes on alcoholic beverages as one of the most cost-effective ways to reduce alcohol consumption to combat alcohol-related diseases, including cardiovascular disease, cancer, and other noncommunicable diseases [7].

At the same time, emerging problems should be noted, which can be grouped into several areas. First, the products in question are important areas of production, creating jobs in the economy while simultaneously generating tax revenue. Representatives of the relevant industries argue that high excise taxes increase illicit trade, push consumers to seek cheaper alternatives, and harm legitimate businesses, leading to job losses and slowing the economy; they can damage a country's business performance rating and are discriminatory. Therefore, public health measures to reduce the consumption of unhealthy products must be balanced with other goals—such as preserving traditional industries, protecting competition and consumer choice, and securing government revenue.

Excise taxes on tobacco and alcohol products account for a very small share of tax revenues – 1.85% in Germany, 2.55% in Finland, 2.6% in Japan, and 3.4% in Hungary. Moreover, declining consumption leads, in turn, to a decline in tax revenues. In this context, it is important that the funds raised are used specifically for healthcare needs, to finance further efforts to improve public health, rather than being siphoned off into a general fund [8].

To achieve this, a targeted funding mechanism is used, which involves taking all or a portion of the total tax revenue and using it to cover specific expenditures. In practice, targeted funding provides expenditure visibility by creating a link between the source of funds and what they are spent on, implying that, all other things being equal, the targeted funds will be sufficient to meet the expenditure needs. Targeted funding can determine what portion of the revenue source should be allocated to the health sector or a targeted program or establish the proportion of funds to be spent on a specific purpose. In 2017, at least 54 countries used targeted funding for health through taxes on the consumption of unhealthy products. About 38 countries allocate some or all of their tobacco taxes to specific health programs [7].

Increasing health spending in developed countries has contributed to significant progress in public health, particularly in increasing life expectancy. Currently, the demand for healthcare services remains unabated, driven primarily by demographic and technological factors. To support existing healthcare systems and ensure their development under severe budget constraints, new sources of funding must be identified. In this context, the following conclusions are important. For the successful implementation of any healthcare financing strategy, coordination between the two key government functions, healthcare and finance and ensuring interaction between the ministries and agencies representing them are crucial.

References

1. Khan, A. A. (2024). The Intersection of Finance and Healthcare: Financing Healthcare Delivery Systems. *Journal of Education and Finance Review*, 1(1), 22-34. <https://doi.org/10.62843/jefr/2022.1715003>
2. World Health Organization. (2021). Global Health Expenditure Database. <https://apps.who.int/nha/database/Select/Indicators/en>
3. Isik, M., & Isik, F. (2015). Analyzing financial structure of Turkish healthcare system in comparison with U.S., German, British, French and Cuban Healthcare Systems. *Pressacademia*, 2(4), 501–501. <https://doi.org/10.17261/pressacademia.2015414364>
4. Färdow J., Broström L., Johansson M. (2019). Co-payment for Unfunded Additional Care in Publicly Funded Healthcare Systems: Ethical Issues // *J Bioeth Inq.*;16(4):515–524.
5. Fusco N., Sils B., Graff J. S., Kistler K., Ruiz K. (2023). Cost-sharing and adherence, clinical outcomes, health care utilization, and costs: A systematic literature review // *J Manag Care Spec Pharm*, volume 29, issue 1, P. 4–16.
6. Kiil A., Houlberg K. (2014). How does copayment for health care services affect demand, health and redistribution? A systematic review of the empirical evidence from 1990 to 2011. // *Eur J Health Econ* 15, 813–828.
7. Miracolo A, Sophiea M., Mackenzie Mills M., Kanavos P. (2021) Sin taxes and their effect on consumption, revenue generation and health improvement: a systematic literature review in Latin America // *Health Policy and Planning*, Volume 36, Issue 5, P. 790–810.
8. Ozer Ceren, Bloom D., Martinez Valle A., Banzon E., Mandeville K., Paul J., Blecher E., Parkes S., Chhabra S. (2020). Health earmarks and health taxes: what do we know? // *HNP GP Knowledge Brief*, World Bank. 7 p.